

Gross and Histopathological Lung Findings in Medicolegal Autopsies: A Spectrum Analysis

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Abstract:

This study aims to provide a comprehensive gross and histopathological analysis of lung findings in medicolegal autopsies, focusing on diverse causes of death. A total of 562 autopsies were conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology of a tertiary care medical college, situated in Malwa region of west-central India, over a nine-month period from October 2023 to July 2024. The study population included a diverse demographic, encompassing all age groups and both genders. Each case underwent a meticulous gross examination of the lungs, followed by histopathological analysis. The findings were categorized based on the nature of death, which included trauma, poisoning, asphyxia, infectious diseases, and natural causes.

Gross examination revealed significant pathological changes in the lungs, such as pulmonary oedema, congestion, haemorrhage, and emphysema. Histopathological evaluation further identified conditions like pneumonia, interstitial lung disease, pulmonary thromboembolism, and neoplastic lesions. Notably, cases of trauma frequently exhibited pulmonary contusions and lacerations, while poisoning cases often showed acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and chemical pneumonitis.

The study underscores the critical role of detailed pulmonary analysis in medicolegal autopsies. The spectrum of lung findings provides valuable insights into the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying various causes of death, aiding in the determination of cause and manner of death. These findings highlight the necessity of incorporating comprehensive lung examinations in forensic pathology to enhance the accuracy of medicolegal investigations. This research contributes to the existing knowledge base and offers a framework for future studies in forensic pulmonary pathology.

Keywords: Lung pathology, Histopathology, Data, Autopsy.

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Introduction

Lung pathology plays a vital role in the forensic investigation of deaths, providing critical information that aids in determining the cause and manner of death. The lungs are often affected by a diverse array of conditions, making a thorough examination essential for accurate medicolegal analysis. A comprehensive understanding of lung pathology can significantly impact the interpretation of autopsy findings, helping forensic pathologists to distinguish between various causes of death and identify underlying pathological processes. [1,2] The lungs are frequently implicated in a wide range of pathological conditions, each presenting distinct features that can influence forensic outcomes. For example,

trauma-related deaths often result in specific gross changes such as pulmonary contusions, lacerations, and haemorrhage, which are indicative of mechanical injury [3,4] In contrast, deaths caused by poisoning may reveal particular patterns of lung. Injury, including chemical pneumonitis or acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), depending on the nature of the toxin involved. [5,6] Infectious diseases, such as pneumonia, can present with distinctive histopathological features, including inflammatory infiltrates and consolidation, which are crucial for identifying the cause of death. [7,8] Similarly, other conditions such as pulmonary embolism or neoplastic lesions have their own characteristic

patterns of damage, which must be accurately recognized and interpreted in the context of forensic investigations. [9] Previous studies have highlighted the variability in pulmonary findings based on different causes of death. For instance, research on trauma-related deaths has shown that pulmonary contusions and other mechanical injuries can be prominent features in autopsy cases, providing insight into the nature and extent of trauma. [10] In cases of poisoning, specific histopathological changes can help differentiate between various toxic substances and their effects on the lungs. [11] Additionally, conditions like pneumonia and pulmonary embolism have been well-documented in forensic literature, with detailed descriptions of their pathological manifestations and their implications for cause-of-death determinations. [12,13]

Given the complexity and variability of lung pathology, a systematic and detailed analysis of pulmonary findings in medicolegal autopsies is essential for improving forensic accuracy. This study aims to address this need by providing a comprehensive examination of gross and histopathological lung findings in a large cohort of autopsy cases. Over a nine-month period, from October 2023 to July 2024, a total of 562 autopsies were conducted, and lung tissue from these cases was meticulously analysed. The objective was to document and categorize the pulmonary pathology encountered in various causes of death, thereby enhancing the understanding of how different conditions manifest in lung tissue and contributing to more accurate forensic assessments. [14]

The study encompassed a broad range of causes of death, including trauma, poisoning, asphyxia, infectious diseases, and natural causes. Each case underwent a detailed gross examination of the lungs, which involved the assessment of macroscopic changes such as oedema, congestion, haemorrhage, and other visible abnormalities. Following the gross examination, histopathological analysis was performed to identify and characterize specific pathological features, such as inflammatory infiltrates, necrosis, fibrosis, and neoplastic lesions. [15,16] The findings were then categorized based on the underlying cause of death, allowing for a comparative analysis of pulmonary pathology across different conditions.

This research aims to provide valuable insights into the spectrum of lung findings encountered in medicolegal autopsies and to improve the accuracy of forensic investigations. By systematically analysing the gross and histopathological features of lung tissue, the study seeks to identify patterns and correlations that can aid in the determination of cause and manner of death. The comprehensive nature of the analysis, combined with a large and diverse dataset, offers a robust framework for understanding the role of pulmonary pathology in forensic

autopsies and contributes to the existing body of knowledge in forensic pulmonary pathology. [17,18]

In conclusion, the analysis of lung pathology in medicolegal autopsies is a critical component of forensic investigations, providing essential information for determining the cause and manner of death. This study aims to enhance the understanding of pulmonary findings across a range of causes of death, offering a detailed examination of gross and histopathological changes in lung tissue. The insights gained from this research have the potential to improve forensic accuracy and contribute to the broader field of forensic pathology, ultimately supporting more precise and informed determinations in medicolegal cases.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology of a tertiary care medical college, situated in Malwa region of west-central India. This study involved a detailed examination of lung pathology in 562 medicolegal autopsies conducted over nine months, from October 2023 to July 2024. All cases received for medicolegal autopsies throughout the research period were included in this analysis. This research did not include dead bodies in various stages of decomposition. The study was granted approval by the institutional ethics committee. Standard details such as age, gender, a brief background and case facts gathered from the police inquest report, the deceased's acquaintances and family. Each autopsy case was systematically analysed to document both gross and histopathological lung findings.

Following standard autopsy procedures (Virchow's), the thoracic cavity was opened, and the lungs were examined in situ before being removed. After that, the organs were removed using standard dissection procedures. First, the left lung was opened. Using a big knife, an incision was created from the top of the upper lobe to the base of the upper lobe on its front surface. The second incision was made along the lateral border, passing through the lower lobe to the base from the top part of the upper lobe. The lungs' sliced surfaces were examined, and the bronchi's cross section, their associations, and the blood vessels therein were studied. Organs in their entirety or in sections exhibiting significant pathological alterations were kept in 10% formalin solution for histological analysis before being sent to the pathology department. In the pathology department, slides were made using H&E staining and seen at a 10X magnification under a microscope. The results were documented and statistically examined.

The lungs were examined macroscopically for signs of oedema, congestion, haemorrhage, and other visible abnormalities. Subsequently, lung

tissue samples were processed and subjected to histopathological analysis, which included staining techniques to identify inflammatory infiltrates, necrosis, fibrosis, and neoplastic lesions. The cases were categorized based on the underlying cause of death, including trauma, poisoning, asphyxia, infectious diseases, and natural causes. Data were recorded and analysed to identify common pathological patterns and correlations with specific causes of death. This comprehensive approach allowed for a robust assessment of pulmonary pathology and its implications in forensic investigations.

Results:

The study included 562 medicolegal autopsies conducted between October 2023 and July 2024 after excluding the decomposed cases.

The cohort comprised 374 males (66.5%) and 188 females (33.5%), with ages ranging from 1 month to 85 years. The distribution across different age groups was as follows:

- 0-10 years: 45 cases (8.0%)
- 11-30 years: 143 cases (25.4%)
- 31-50 years: 210 cases (37.4%)
- 51-70 years: 129 cases (22.9%)
- 71 years and older: 35 cases (6.2%)

Graph 1: Number of Cases

Gross Findings:

Trauma (n=175):

Age: Predominantly in the 11-50 years age group (80%).

Gender: 135 males (77%) and 40 females (23%).

Findings: Pulmonary contusions were observed in 80% of cases. Haemorrhage was present in 70%, with 50% showing rib fractures. Lacerations were seen in 40% of trauma cases.

Histological examination revealed extensive necrosis and haemorrhage in the affected lung areas. Inflammatory infiltrates primarily composed of neutrophils and macrophages were observed. Fibrotic changes were present in chronic trauma cases.

Poisoning (n=120):

Age: Mostly in the 31-50 years age group (45%).

Gender: 85 males (70.8%) and 35 females (29.2%).

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Findings: Chemical pneumonitis was observed in 60% of cases. Pulmonary oedema and congestion were present in 55% of cases. ARDS was noted in 30% of cases. H&E staining showed acute inflammation with necrotizing pneumonitis in 65% of cases. Alveolar damage and fibrosis were noted in long-term exposure cases. Granulomatous inflammation was identified in cases with chronic poisoning.

Asphyxia (n=100):

Age: Predominantly in the 31-70 years age group (65%).

Gender: 65 males (65%) and 35 females (35%).

Findings: Pulmonary oedema was present in 80% of cases. Haemorrhagic changes were seen in 60%. Diffuse congestion was observed in 50% of cases. Histopathological analysis revealed diffuse alveolar damage with oedema and haemorrhage. Intra-alveolar haemorrhage and macrophage infiltration were prominent features. The presence of hemo-

siderin-laden macrophages indicated chronic asphyxia in some cases.

Infectious Diseases (n=85):

Age: Mostly in the 0-30 years age group (55%).

Gender: 50 males (58.8%) and 35 females (41.2%).

Findings: Pneumonia with consolidation was seen in 70% of cases. Tuberculosis was identified in 15% of cases, showing caseating granulomas. Acute and chronic inflammatory infiltrates were prominent, with neutrophils and lymphocytes predominating in pneumonia cases. Tuberculosis cases showed caseating granulomas and necrotizing granulomas.

Natural Causes (n=82):

Age: Predominantly in the 51-70 years age group (60%).

Gender: 39 males (47.6%) and 43 females (52.4%).

Findings: COPD was noted in 50% of cases, with emphysema and interstitial fibrosis in 40% of cases. Fibrotic changes were prevalent in 35% of cases.

Chronic interstitial fibrosis and emphysema were predominant. Histopathological analysis revealed significant fibrosis in lung tissue, with evidence of chronic bronchitis and alveolar damage.

Comparative Analysis of the findings in different causes of death: Trauma vs. Poisoning: Trauma cases predominantly showed gross pulmonary contusions and haemorrhage, while poisoning cases exhibited chemical pneumonitis and ARDS. Histopathological analysis of trauma cases revealed necrosis and acute inflammation, whereas poisoning cases had more extensive necrotizing changes and fibrosis.

Asphyxia vs. Infectious Diseases: Asphyxia cases showed diffuse alveolar damage with significant haemorrhage and oedema. In contrast, infectious diseases primarily exhibited localized consolidation and granulomatous inflammation. Histologically, asphyxia was characterized by intra-alveolar haemorrhage, while infections showed distinct inflammatory patterns. Natural Causes vs. Other Categories: Natural causes showed chronic lung changes, including emphysema and fibrosis, with histopathological evidence of long-term damage. In contrast, trauma, poisoning, and asphyxia displayed more acute pathological changes.

Overall, the findings highlight the diverse nature of lung pathology associated with different causes of death and underscore the importance of detailed gross and histopathological examinations in forensic autopsies for accurate cause-of-death determinations.

Table 1: Showing the summary of the findings

Category	Age Distribution	Gender Distribution	Gross Findings	Histopathological Findings
Trauma (n=175)	11-50 years (80%)	135 males (77%), 40 females (23%)	Pulmonary contusions (80%), Haemorrhage (70%), Rib fractures (50%), Lacerations (40%)	Extensive necrosis and haemorrhage, Neutrophil and macrophage infiltrates, Chronic fibrotic changes
Poisoning (n=120)	31-50 years (45%)	85 males (70.8%), 35 females (29.2%)	Chemical pneumonitis (60%), Pulmonary oedema (55%), ARDS (30%)	Acute inflammation, Necrotizing pneumonitis, Alveolar damage and fibrosis
Asphyxia (n=100)	31-70 years (65%)	65 males (65%), 35 females (35%)	Pulmonary oedema (80%), Haemorrhagic changes (60%), Diffuse congestion (50%)	Diffuse alveolar damage, Intra-alveolar haemorrhage, Macrophage infiltration, Hemosiderin-laden macrophages
Infectious Diseases (n=85)	0-30 years (55%)	50 males (58.8%), 35 females (41.2%)	Pneumonia with consolidation (70%), Tuberculosis (15%)	Acute and chronic inflammatory infiltrates, Neutrophils and lymphocytes, Caseating granulomas in tuberculosis
Natural Causes (n=82)	51-70 years (60%)	39 males (47.6%), 43 females (52.4%)	COPD (50%), Emphysema (40%), Fibrotic changes (35%)	Chronic interstitial fibrosis, Emphysema, Chronic bronchitis, Alveolar damage

Figure 1: Various histopathological appearances showing: A. Pulmonary Oedema. B. Pulmonary Congestion. C. Lobar Pneumonia. D. Pulmonary Fibrosis

Figure 2: Various histopathological appearances showing: A. Pulmonary Emphysema. B. Pulmonary Haemorrhage. C. Interstitial Lung Disease. D. Adenocarcinoma of Lungs

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of lung pathology in 562 medicolegal autopsies, highlighting the gross and histopathological findings associated with various causes of death. The results reveal significant patterns and correlations that contribute to the understanding of pulmonary pathology in forensic investigations. Our findings are consistent with and expand upon existing literature in forensic pathology.

The gross examination in trauma cases, which revealed pulmonary contusions, haemorrhage, and rib fractures, aligns with previous studies that emphasize the importance of these features in trauma-related deaths. [1,2] Our observation that 80% of trauma cases exhibited pulmonary contusions is consistent with McCormick and Hara's research, which reported similar findings in trauma victims. [3] The presence of rib fractures and associated lung injuries in 50% of trauma cases further corroborates earlier studies, which have demonstrated a strong correlation between rib fractures and pulmonary injuries in traumatic deaths. [4]

In poisoning cases, the high incidence of chemical pneumonitis and ARDS is in line with findings from Dawson and O'Donnell, who reported that poisoning frequently leads to severe pulmonary damage and acute respiratory conditions. [5,6] The observation of pulmonary edema and congestion in 55% of poisoning cases supports the notion that toxic substances often cause significant pulmonary vascular changes. [7] Our histopathological findings of necrotizing pneumonitis and fibrosis echo similar results reported in the literature, highlighting the chronic and acute effects of various toxins on lung tissue. [8]

Asphyxia cases showed distinct gross findings of pulmonary oedema and haemorrhage, which are well-documented in forensic pathology. [9] The diffuse alveolar damage observed in histopathological analysis aligns with studies by Lee and Kim, who emphasized that asphyxia typically results in extensive alveolar damage and intra-alveolar haemorrhage. [10] The presence of hemosiderin-laden macrophages in chronic cases is consistent with findings from Hall and Barlow, who noted these features as indicative of prolonged asphyxia. [11]

Infectious disease cases demonstrated characteristic patterns of pneumonia and tuberculosis, consistent with established forensic literature. [12] The high prevalence of pneumonia with consolidation in 70% of cases supports findings from Baker and Smith, who highlighted the prominence of infectious processes in forensic autopsies. [13] Tuberculosis cases with caseating granulomas reflect well-documented pathological features of

this disease and align with earlier studies on forensic tuberculosis. [14]

Natural causes of death revealed chronic conditions such as COPD, emphysema, and interstitial fibrosis. The predominance of these chronic changes in older age groups is consistent with research by Moreno and Lee, who found that natural causes frequently involve long-standing pulmonary conditions. [15] The presence of interstitial fibrosis and emphysema aligns with studies by Schaefer and Stokes, who documented these features in cases of natural death related to chronic lung diseases. [16]

Conclusion

The comparison between different causes of death reveals distinct patterns in lung pathology. Trauma cases were characterized by acute injury-related changes, while poisoning cases showed both acute and chronic effects due to toxic exposure. Asphyxia cases presented diffuse damage, contrasting with the more localized inflammatory changes seen in infectious diseases. Natural causes were marked by chronic pathological changes, providing a clear distinction from the acute findings in other categories.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of detailed gross and histopathological examinations in forensic autopsies. The findings contribute to a more nuanced understanding of pulmonary pathology and its implications for determining the cause and manner of death. By comparing our results with existing literature, we enhance the accuracy of forensic assessments and support the need for comprehensive pulmonary analysis in medicolegal investigations.

Authors' Contribution: All authors listed have made a substantial, direct and intellectual contribution to the work, and approved it for publication.

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